

EFFECTS OF NOISE ON PERFORMANCE AND PERCEIVED ANNOYANCE IN STROOP TASKS

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ABSTRACT

Psychoacoustic laboratory investigations of annoyance from prolonged exposure to environmental noise stimuli may require that subjects are engaged in a cognitive task while being exposed to the noise. This setup for collecting subjective annoyance represents a so-called unfocused listening experiment. Thereby, annoyance ratings would be collected after noise playback. Finding appropriate tasks, however, can be challenging. Firstly, doing a monotonous task for prolonged periods of time could be tiresome. Secondly, learning effects due to repetition(s) may bias the results. Hence, it is desirable to incorporate similar tasks of comparable difficulty, that can be used interchangeably, and the performance of which should not be affected by noise differently. The objective of the present study was to test whether different versions of the so-called Stroop task fulfill these requirements. In two pilot experiments, several variations of the Stroop task were tested regarding the two criteria of task similarity and comparable difficulty. Based on the results, two types of Stroop task were selected for the main experiment. Here, subjects were seated in a genuine office repurposed for this experiment, whilst performing the different versions of the Stroop task in three sound conditions: silence ($L_{Aeq} = 26$ dBA), low-level background sound of birds and vegetation ($L_{Aeq} = 32$ dBA), and road traffic noise superimposed on the mentioned background sound ($L_{Aeq} = 45$ dBA). Reaction times and error rates were measured. After the experiment, subjects were asked which sounds they found the least and the most annoying. Although no significant differences were found in Stroop task performance between the three sound conditions, annoyance judgements differed: road traffic noise was found to be more annoying than silence or background sound. We conclude that the chosen versions of the Stroop task are suitable for unfocused listening experiments on annoyance.

1. INTRODUCTION

A considerable number of investigations regarding the health impact of environmental noise, e.g., noise annoyance, are conducted as psychoacoustic laboratory experiments. Acoustic stimuli with relatively short duration (e.g.,

under one minute) can be easily investigated in a focused listening experiment setup [1–5]. That is, when the subject attentively listens to the sound stimuli in sequence and rates them with respect to subjectively perceived annoyance. However, subjective assessment of the sound scenarios (i.e., stimuli) with considerably longer durations would be more appropriately done in unfocused (or non-focused) listening experiment setups [6–9]. That is, during sound playback, the subject carries out a task. After the playback (and the task), the subject is required to rate their perceived annoyance or disturbance by the sound. A crucial point in such a setup is the task itself. While from an experimental point of view, and in order to have the exact same working condition for different sound stimuli, it would be ideal to use the same task repeatedly in the course of an experiment, it would be tiring for the subjects to do a monotonous task for a long time. Another disadvantage would be the learning effect due to repetition, which may bias the results. Therefore, it is desirable to find similar tasks of comparable difficulty. At the same time, the performance in these distinct tasks should not be affected by noise differently. Only if these requisites are satisfied, it could be assured that the tasks could be interchangeably used in the course of an unfocused psychoacoustic laboratory experiment. To that aim, this paper investigates a well-established cognitive-psychological task which fulfills the above-mentioned criteria, namely, the so-called Stroop task.

The Stroop effect occurs when a word that semantically represents a color (e.g., the word red) shows on a monitor screen in a different color (e.g., the color blue) or in the same color (here: the color red) and a subject is asked to respond to (i.e., to identify) either the word or color. Typically, it takes longer to respond when there is a conflict (e.g., the word red shaded blue, called “incongruent”) than when there is no conflict (e.g., the word red shaded red, called “congruent”). This cognitive interference resulting in a conflict within a mismatched stimulus is the Stroop effect [10, 11]. This phenomenon first rose to prominence in 1935 when J. R. Stroop used it in a psychology experiment displaying this interference effect [10].

Later, other types of the Stroop test were proposed [11], including the Simon test [12], whereby a triangle would appear, e.g., above or below a reference point, pointing ei-

ther upward or downward. The subject would have to press a button, such as the up-arrow key or the down-arrow key. Imagine the subject was asked to respond to the direction of the arrow. In that scenario, the incongruent case would be when the arrow is pointing upward but is below the reference point and the subject must press the up-arrow key to indicate arrow's direction. That is, the Simon effect is the interference experienced in giving a response that could be "spatially" incompatible with the stimulus as opposed to the Stroop effect where there is an incompatibility in the stimulus itself [13].

Another type of Stroop task is the "shape" Stroop task in which a shape appears on the screen with a name attached to it. The semantic meaning (i.e., the word) and the graphic meaning (i.e., the shape) of the stimulus can be either congruent or incongruent. For example, the word circle could be written in a rectangle [14].

The reason the Stroop-like tasks were chosen in this study was because of its excellent reliability of the basic Stroop scores with repeated administrations [15]. Even if the presentation is partially modified, such as in [16] where the color word was printed as three letter abbreviations (i.e., "pur" instead of purple or "ora" instead of orange), written horizontally or vertically, no significant difference was found in their response times when compared to the classic Stroop task. Even when, in another study, only the first letter was used (e.g., "o" for orange shown in purple ink), a small interference effect was still present [17].

The aim of this study was to identify Stroop tasks of comparable difficulty that are not affected by noise differently. The application of the Stroop-like tasks in unfocused listening experiments was investigated under laboratory conditions. Two pilot experiments with solely visual stimuli (a Stroop task) and a main experiment with visual as well as acoustic stimuli (i.e., Stroop tasks accompanied with acoustic stimuli in the background) will be presented in the following sections of this paper.

2. EXPERIMENTAL CONCEPT

The first two experiments in this paper are pilot experiments (without any acoustic stimuli) whose objective was to find suitable variations of the Stroop task for the main experiment. After two types of Stroop tasks were chosen based on the results of the pilot experiments, the main experiment, which was conducted to measure subjectively perceived annoyance in unfocused listening conditions, dealt with the effects of sound on perceived annoyance during the visual cognitive tasks, as well as on cognitive performance in the chosen types of the Stroop task.

The visual cognitive tests were prepared in the Python-based PsychoPy software environment [18, 19] and presented to subjects in a quiet experimental room. The Stroop task stimuli were presented on a monitor screen and responses were given on a keyboard using the four arrow keys. Subjects took part in the experiments individually. They were asked about their momentary health, visual cognitive ability (e.g., not colorblind), and, in the case of the main experiment, hearing ability (i.e., inclusion criteria).

The following wordings will be used throughout the paper regarding the visual cognitive tests. One paradigm was used in all three experiments, namely, the Stroop paradigm. Three different "types" of the Stroop test were prepared: spatial, shape, and color tests. For each Stroop type, there were two different tasks; i.e., responding to either aspect of the stimulus (e.g., color or word). Stimuli in all these tasks fell into one of the two categories "congruent" vs. "incongruent" stimuli; i.e., the two aspects of a stimulus were either in harmony with each other (e.g., the word red written in red ink) or competing (i.e. different from each other), respectively. Furthermore, several versions of each Stroop test type was used; i.e., for example a number of different colors were used in different versions of the color Stroop test.

3. PILOT EXPERIMENTS

The pilot experiments aimed at finding out which Stroop tasks would be interchangeable with each other in the context of an unfocused listening experiment. Their purpose was to determine whether the Stroop effect could be replicated with the used software and setup and to identify which versions of the Stroop tasks were similar to one another in terms of the average response time.

Two pilot experiments will be presented in the following. The second pilot experiment (Section 3.2) was necessary because the first pilot experiment (Section 3.1) did not yield the expected Stroop effect (note: the primary Stroop effect is that the response time is higher for incongruent stimuli than for the congruent stimuli). In the first and the second experiment, two and three alternatives were given to the subjects in each task, respectively. That is, for example, in the first experiment the color (and word) red was tested against the color (and word) blue, while in the second experiment the colors (and words) red, yellow, and green were tested against each other.

3.1 First pilot experiment

3.1.1 Design and stimuli

Three types of Stroop tasks were used in the first experiment, each presenting two competing aspects of the visual stimuli (see Figure 1).

- Spatial test (sp.): subjects were presented with arrows on the screen. They were asked to identify either the direction, i.e., towards left vs. towards right (or alternatively upward vs. downward) or the position, i.e., left side of the screen vs. right side of the screen (or alternatively in the bottom of the screen vs. on the top of the screen) of the arrow [12, 13].
- Shape test (sh.): subjects were asked to identify either the shape of the object or the word written inside the object [14].
- Color test (co.): subjects were asked to identify either the color of the visual stimulus or the semantic meaning of it [10].

Figure 1: Examples of the visual stimuli of the spatial (above), the shape (middle) or the color (below) tasks. Congruent and incongruent stimuli are shown left and right, respectively.

Figure 1 shows examples of the three types of visual stimuli. All in all, twelve tests were prepared: three types of Stroop tests with two different tasks (as described above) and in two versions (e.g., for the shape test: “circle vs. rectangle” and “triangle vs. square”). Note that all the tests had a pool of two options to choose from, e.g., “circle vs. rectangle” or “yellow vs. purple.”

Subjects started with a 1.5-min practice session to familiarize themselves with the test. In a complete block design, each subject did all twelve Stroop-like tests, which were each 2 min long. Instructions were presented to the subject before each test, and an *i* button was present in the top left corner of the screen during the task to show subjects a short instruction of the current task if they forgot. The first pilot experiment lasted approximately 40 min. No acoustic background conditions were used in this experiment as the focus was the Stroop task. Accordingly, no subjective annoyance ratings were collected.

3.1.2 Subjects

Twenty-three subjects participated in the first pilot experiment (7 females and 15 males). They were aged between 21 and 58 years (median 35).

3.1.3 Results

The primary Stroop effect was not observed in the first pilot experiment (see Figure 2): there was no significant difference between the response times for the congruent stimuli and the incongruent stimuli ($p > 0.05$). This outcome was observed for all twelve Stroop tests (all $p > 0.05$).

Figure 2: Results of pilot experiment 1 – mean response time across subjects and Stroop tests and 95% confidence intervals as a function of the variable congruency.

However, on average, subjects made significantly more errors in the case of incongruent stimuli than in the case of congruent stimuli ($p < 0.01$). Furthermore, as shown in Figure 3, significant differences were observed in response times between a number of tasks when pooled over congruent and incongruent treatments ($p < 0.01$).

3.2 Second pilot experiment

3.2.1 Design and stimuli

The results of the first experiment raised the question whether the task had been too easy with only two alternatives (e.g., red vs. blue) – since no significant difference was found, on average, between the response times for the congruent and the incongruent cases. A second pilot experiment was, therefore, designed with a pool including three options for each test version. The three bottom arrow keys (left, down, and right) on the keyboard were used for the second experiment.

It was decided to continue with the shape and color tests, and to eliminate the spatial test. This was, on the one hand, because the response times for the two spatial tasks (i.e., to identify either the direction or the position of the arrow) were significantly different (see Figure 3) and, on the other hand, because the spatial test could not be easily expanded to having three options.

In the color type test, three colors were used: yellow, red, and green. In the shape type test, three shapes were used: square, circle, and triangle. Similar to the tasks in the first experiment, two different tasks were given to the subjects, one asking for the written word, the other asking for the shape or color. From these combinations, all in all, four tests were prepared for the second pilot experiment, each 2 min long.

Subjects started with a 1-min practice session to familiarize themselves with the test. In a complete block design, each subject did all four Stroop tests. The second pilot experiment lasted approximately 20 min. Similar to the first pilot experiment, no acoustic background conditions were used in this experiment as the focus was the Stroop task. Accordingly, no subjective annoyance ratings were collected.

Figure 3: Results of pilot experiment 1 – mean response time across subjects and 95% confidence intervals as a function of the variable Stroop test. sp., sh., and co. represent spatial, shape, and color types, respectively. Furthermore, hor., ver., RC, ST, YP, and RB, stand for the horizontal, vertical, rectangular-circle, square-triangle, yellow-purple, and red-blue versions, respectively. Finally, d, p, s, w, and c denote the tasks to identify direction, position, shape, word, or color, respectively.

Figure 4: Results of pilot experiment 2 – mean response time across subjects and Stroop tests and 95% confidence intervals as a function of the variable congruency.

Figure 5: Results of pilot experiment 2 – mean response time across subjects and congruency and 95% confidence intervals as a function of the variable Stroop test, denoted in the form of “type-task.”

3.2.2 Subjects

Fifteen subjects participated in the second pilot experiment (2 females and 13 males). They were aged between 18 and 62 years (median 33).

3.2.3 Results

Figure 4 shows a significant effect of the congruency on the response time ($p < 0.01$); i.e., the Stroop effect. On average, the subjects took longer to respond to the incongruent stimuli than to the congruent stimuli. They made significantly more errors in the case of incongruent stimuli than for the congruent stimuli ($p < 0.01$). Furthermore, as shown in Figure 5, the most similar tests in terms of average response times were the shape Stroop test asking for the shape (i.e., shape-shape) and the classic Stroop test asking for the word (i.e., color-word). Mean response times across subjects for these two Stroop tests were not significantly different from each other ($p > 0.05$). The results of the second pilot experiment led to the conclusion that these two types of Stroop tests (and tasks) – i.e., the shape-shape and the color-word tests – were suitable for interchangeable use in unfocused listening experiment setups due to the insignificance in difference between their reaction times.

4. MAIN EXPERIMENT

In the main experiment, it was investigated whether the Stroop test is a suitable task for unfocused listening experiment setups for noise annoyance studies.

4.1 Design and stimuli

In an office setup in a quiet experimental room, a loudspeaker (KH120 A, Georg Neumann GmbH, Berlin, Germany) was placed in front of a (closed) window and 3.5 m behind subjects' head, who was seated at a desk in front of a keyboard and a monitor screen. The setup simulated an open window from which the sounds would enter the office. Three sound categories were used: no background sound, background sound of birds and vegetation, and road traffic noise (including background sound of birds and vegetation). At subjects' (sitting) ear level, they had L_{Aeq} of 26, 32, and 45 dBA, respectively.

The road traffic noise stimulus originated from car pass-by recordings made by the Empa in the course of a previous study [3]. The background sounds of birds and vegetation originated from recordings carried out in the course of another previous study [5].

Four Stroop tests were used in the main experiment

Figure 6: Results of the main experiment – mean response time across subjects, Stroop tests and sounds and 95% confidence intervals as a function of the variable congruency.

which are described in the form of “type-task” in the following.

- ST1: shape-shape (i.e., shape type, responding to the shape of the stimulus) with rectangle, star, and circle;
- ST2: shape-shape with square, triangle, and oval;
- ST3: color-word (i.e., color type, responding to the written word) with red, blue, and yellow;
- ST4: color-word with purple, green, and orange.

The combination of the three sound situations and four Stroop tests resulted in twelve treatments of 2.5 min each. Subjects started with a 1-min practice session to familiarize themselves with the experimental setup and the task. In a partially balanced incomplete block design (PBIBD), each subject only did eight of these twelve treatments. The entire session lasted approximately 30 min.

At the end of the unfocused listening experiment, subjects were handed a questionnaire with two experimental questions.

- Question 1: Could you describe the types of sound situations you heard during the experiment, each in 1–2 word(s)?
- Question 2: Which sound situation did you find least and most annoying/disturbing?

Their answers to the second question were coded as 1, 2, and 3 for the least annoying, in between, and the most annoying sounds, respectively.

4.2 Subjects

Twenty-two subjects participated in the main experiment (11 females and 11 males). They were aged between 24 and 58 years (median 28.5).

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Task performance

Figure 6 shows a significant effect of congruency on the response time ($p < 0.01$); i.e., the Stroop effect. In accordance with the results of the second experiment, on average, the subjects took longer to respond to the incongruent

Figure 7: Results of the main experiment – mean response time across subjects and sounds and 95% confidence intervals as a function of the variable Stroop test, denoted as ST1 to ST4 (see Section 4.1).

Figure 8: Results of the main experiment – mean response time across subjects and Stroop tests and 95% confidence intervals as a function of the acoustic stimuli. BGS refers to the background sound.

stimuli than to the congruent stimuli ($p < 0.01$). Furthermore, they made significantly more errors in incongruent cases than in congruent cases ($p < 0.01$). In Figure 7, the response time is depicted as a function of the Stroop test (ST1–ST4). Although significant differences can be observed between Stroop tasks, the mean differences are much smaller than the results of the pilot experiments (see Figures 3 and 5 for comparison). This indicates the relatively similar difficulty of the tasks with respect to the response time.

Figure 8 illustrates that sound did not have an effect on Stroop task performance, measured as response time ($p > 0.05$). Furthermore, sound had no significant influence on the error rate ($p > 0.05$).

4.3.2 Annoyance

Subjects’ responses to Question 1 (i.e., “Could you describe the types of sound situations you heard during the experiment, each in 1–2 word(s)?”) were noticeably similar. They described the three sound situations as quiet/quietness/silence, garden/birds/nature, and car/traffic. Only three subjects failed to identify the road traffic noise and described it as water stream or as aircraft noise.

On average, silence, background sound (of birds and vegetation), and road traffic noise were rated as 1.57, 1.57, and 2.86, respectively. That is, road traffic noise was rated to be significantly more annoying than the other two sound

scenarios. Note that these are annoyance rankings, not absolute annoyance ratings.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Two pilot and one main experiments were presented here, investigating visual cognitive tasks based on the Stroop test. A pool of three alternating options was necessary to replicate the primary expected Stroop test output; i.e., longer response times for the incongruent stimuli than for the congruent stimuli. The results indicate that the Stroop-like tests are suitable for unfocussed listening experiments in the context of environmental acoustics. Subjects were able to rank their annoyance from acoustic stimuli at the end of the experimental session, after they were busy with variations of the Stroop task during sound playbacks. Sound stimuli had no significant effect on task performance, measured as average response time or average error rate in the cognitive task. We conclude that variations of the Stroop test might not deliver reliable objective measures of noise annoyance (or that performance in Stroop task might only have a mediating effect on annoyance). However, they should be appropriate tasks when investigating perceived noise annoyance in unfocussed listening experiment setups.

6. REFERENCES

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS The authors are grateful to the subjects of the pilot and the main experiments.

DECLARATION This research was funded by the Swiss Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN). The experiments have been approved by Empa’s Ethics Committee.

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